

In-depth analysis and enhanced host-based Intrusion Detection Using Combined Machine Learning and Open-Source Security Tools.

Nibretu Kebede¹

Gebeyehu Belay Gebremeskel^{2*}

Kenaw Ambachew Goshu³

1. Debre Tabor University; Department of Information Technology, Gafat Institute of Technology, Debre Tabor. Ethiopia, kebedenibretu@gmail.com
2. Bahir Dar University Institute of Technology, Main Campus, Ghion Building, 3rd floor, 313, Bahir Dar. Ethiopia, gebeyheu2009@gmail.com, and correspondence author
3. Woldia University, College of Informatics, Woldia, Ethiopia, kenawambachew1212@gmail.com

Abstract: Computer networks have made the world a small village. However, this sophisticated and ever-growing communication network has suffered from rapidly increasing attacks (intrusions). Various solutions have low detection rates, high false positives, high processing time, large trace sizes, and other challenges. This study proposes using machine learning and open-source security tools to explore host-based intrusion detection systems. The research conducts an in-depth analysis of evasion attacks, anomaly-based techniques, and signature misuse-based approaches. The Australian Defense Force Academy Linux dataset for Features is selected from the ADFA-LD dataset using the N-gram feature extraction mechanism. It configures one of the host-based intrusion detection tools for open-source, security-signature-based intrusion detection. The experiment shows that the proposed approach is promising in terms of detection rate, false-positive rate, and processing time. These three machine learning algorithms are SVM, KNN, and RF for classification, and they achieved better performance in binary classification than in multi-class classification. The experimental accuracy of SVM is 96.26% with a 5.1% false-positive rate (FPR), KNN is 96.71% with 3.28% FPR, and RF is 96.86% with 3.9% FPR.

Keywords: Host-based intrusion detection, Open-source security, Machine learning algorithms, False alarm rates

1. Introduction

AI/ machine learning-based Intrusion Detection Systems (IDSs) are an active and prioritized research area. Machine learning plays a crucial role in the ongoing fight against cyberattacks, continuously enhancing intrusion detection and safeguarding computer networks. Intruders exploit system vulnerabilities to gain unauthorized access, steal information, or disrupt services (Kim et al., 2014). Effective intrusion detection is vital; it involves monitoring network activity to identify and alert operators to potential security policy violations (Karen and Peter, 2007). An IDS specifically examines these security threats within a computer network (Nilotpal, 2013), relying on established security practices and policies to identify incident threats.

Network-based IDS (NIDS) is essential for overseeing network traffic from all connected devices. These systems are strategically placed at key points within the network, acting like watchful guards (Waidyarathna et al., 2018). Their primary job is to detect any unusual or unwanted activities happening across the network (Urooj et al., 2017; Ramprakash et al., 2014), alerting administrators to potential threats. In contrast, a HIDS focuses its attention on individual systems or devices. It constantly monitors for intrusive activity, aiming to identify any intrusion alarms directly on the host. When it detects suspicious behavior, it's designed to determine if the message indicates an actual attack. A HIDS observes incoming and outgoing data packets from the device and generates an alert whenever suspicious activity is detected. Beyond just monitoring traffic, a HIDS tool or system can also take snapshots of the current system files and compare them to previous versions to spot any unauthorized changes.

Machine learning is a predictive model development algorithm that enhances the ability to detect attacks. Machine learning algorithms can be integrated with smart security tools (open-source security) for Intrusion Detection mechanisms (Hani et al., 2023). Machine learning for cybersecurity improves the detection rate and reduces false positives by creating intelligent detection mechanisms (Zeeshan et al., 2020). Support Vector Machine (SVM), K-nearest neighbor (KNN), and Random Forest (RF) are machine learning algorithms used to classify call traces (data) into attack or non-attack classes (Syed et al., 2015; Indu et al., 2013). In traditional intrusion detection, the process is challenging without extensive human knowledge of attack scenarios. Additionally, classical intrusion detection

involves manual activities to update the database for every new type of intrusion discovered (Abeer et al., 2023). This complexity makes signature-based detection for the database more challenging to implement. The challenges include: (i) how to pre-process and extract features from raw system call data sets for anomaly-based host intrusion detection, (ii) developing a hybrid model for improved detection with minimal false alarms using machine learning algorithms, and (integrating open-source security (OSSEC) tools with machine learning and applying them to host-based IDS.

This paper aims to develop a host-based intrusion detection model for effective defense against known attacks. The contributions of the paper are the following:

- Enhancing IDS mechanisms using machine learning and open-source security tools to classify system behavior and detect attacks or non-attacks.
- Performing an in-depth analysis of Anomaly Detection mechanisms by classifying events for groups of IDS call sequences using Support Vector Machine, K-nearest neighbor, and Random Forest classification algorithms.
- Develop a novel detection model to enhance the IDS performance using machine learning to introduce a system to rank and diverge the visual differences in system-call n-grams.
- Proposed a novel solution based on anomaly detection under numerical and categorical features, to obtain a lightweight anomaly-detection stage deployable on resource-constrained devices, and
- Finally, to evaluate the model using the Australian Defense Force Academy Linux dataset, which is suitable for the integrity of machine learning with other soft tools via open-source security for in-depth IDS analysis.

The paper is organized into seven sections. Section 1: An introduction outlining the research content. Section 2 presents related works offering an in-depth overview of the IDS and Machine learning algorithms applied to security issues. Section 3 describes the methodology and design of a model procedure. Section 4 focuses on data preparation and representation, discussing aspects of feature selection and predictive model building, algorithms, and open-source security tools. Section 5 covers model performance evaluation metrics. Section 6 presents a thorough discussion of the experiments and results. Finally, Section 7 offers the conclusion, followed by acknowledgments and references.

2. Related works

The intrusion detection systems are broadly classified into Host-Based Intrusion Detection Systems (HBIDS) and Network-Based Intrusion Detection Systems (NIDS) based on their information sources (Jiankun, 2010). The most common types are network-based IDS and host-based IDS, which focus on the physical targets of the distributed IDS, hypervisor-based IDS, and hybrid IDS. NIDS collects input data by monitoring network traffic (Sheikh et al., 2019). On the network, the data traveling to and from the devices is controlled and analyzed for intrusion or fault detection (Abebe and Lalitha, 2015; Jayshree and Leena, 2013). The NIDS process is passive and informs about an intrusion by an administrator when an attack has already taken place (Santos et al., 2013), which will not be sufficient for an Intrusion Prevention System (IPS) to react and be able to block the detected doubtful traffic (Kopelo et al., 2013).

Many researchers have studied IDS on Network-based IDS to address data encryption limitations in each packet of the message in the network (Yousef et al., 2014; Kamlesh, 2013). Host-based IDS is the first and best alternative for securing data from particular systems, securing challenges that have been designed and implemented as software agents (Bilal and Peer, 2011). Network packet design and analysis are based on the behavior of applications on the host, observing the interaction with the underlying operating system. HIDS(s) rely on events collected by the host's networks (Robin et al., 2020; Abdullah, 2013). NIDS is essential for checking and analyzing the internals of computer network packets on its interfaces using information acquired from inside a system that includes audit files in the operating system (Anna et al., 2021; Jiankun, 2010). HIDS analyzes the actual activities with great precision and determines the processes in a particular attack. Optimal accuracy gains in the Integrity of NIDS, HIDS, or the Hybrid IDS system are designed (Snehal and Deepti, 2015). The hybrid IDS is a multiple-component system that resides in different nodes on the network (Giampaolo et al., 2020)

For computer network intrusion detection, algorithms, such as image block-matching (Abdullah, 2013) and those

derived from Internet of Things (IoT) and Mobile Ad hoc contexts (Vasaki et al., 2022) have been applied to NSL-KDD datasets. However, the findings from these applications tend to be more specific and focused on industrial control systems (Ines et al., 2022). Detecting intrusion in dynamic systems often requires integrated techniques for improved results. For instance, Gideon (2014) applied contiguous and discontinuous system call patterns on the ADFa Linux data set to reduce the intrusion fault and alarm rates. Nevertheless, this study's testing mechanisms were deemed insufficient, as they didn't address the system's inherent resilience. This oversight makes such approaches less effective for security, particularly when dealing with sparse trace calls for data behavior in anomaly detection (Sheikh et al., 2019). Other researchers have proposed advanced IDS methodologies; for example, Marcin et al. (2021) applied a multivariable heuristic approach. Attacks flag shared data. Muhammad and Kim (2021) implemented deep learning on the ISCX-2012 dataset (from the Canadian Institute of Cybersecurity), achieving better intrusion detection through an intelligent approach (Tariq et al., 2024). Waidyarathna et al. (2018) investigated machine learning for intrusion detection by analyzing incoming messages in computer networks to assess performance acceptance. Despite these advancements, challenges persist. For example, Waqas et al. (2016) used Zero-Day and Stealth attack techniques on the ADFa Linux dataset. Their findings showed similarity between attack and no-attack scenarios, complicating the attainment of maximum precision or accuracy in the detection process.

3. Methodology and Proposed Model Design Algorithms

The methodology of this paper aims to present the detailed workflow and contents that focus on the techniques and proposed model development procedures. Those qualities make the integrity of machine learning and open-source security tools a perfect combination for IDS, which requires vetting through huge amounts of data to distinguish normal and abnormal behaviors. The details are presented in the following sub-section.

3.1. Machine Learning for Intrusion Detection Model Building

Intrusion detection data is essential for developing a policy to investigate violations. However, achieving acceptable accuracy in intrusion detection proves challenging, whether dealing with limited suspicion records or large-scale data analysis. This difficulty primarily stems from the inability to adequately analyze and extract relevant knowledge for informed decision-making (Reem and Mossa, 2020). Machine learning-based IDSs offer a promising solution. They demonstrate strong capabilities in detection and classification, along with efficient generalizability for distinguishing between attack and non-attack scenarios (Aruna et al., 2015; Revathi and Malathi, 2013). As a well-established predictive method, ML excels at uncovering new knowledge through experimentation. The algorithms propose enhancing computer tools and software agents that leverage ML and data mining for analyzing data to build robust intrusion detection models (Vasaki et al., 2022; Robin et al., 2020). These methods are designed to provide valuable insights. In this research, authors specifically use ADF-LD data to test and evaluate the proposed model's performance, offering insights for host-based anomaly intrusion detection (Christian et al., 2017; Amrit and Manik, 2014).

Machine learning algorithms are increasingly vital for developing intrusion detection systems (IDS) due to their independence from specific domain knowledge and ease of design (Abeer et al., 2023). These algorithms, including Support Vector Machine (SVM), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), and Random Forest (RF), are frequently employed in intensive, iterative experiments for anomaly-based detection and other forms of intrusion detection (Liu and Lang, 2019). ML techniques have become indispensable in network cybersecurity, effectively tackling pattern recognition challenges within large anomaly detection (Kayode et al., 2024; Yisroel et al., 2018). Furthermore, ML plays a significant role in reducing computational cost functions and optimizing the learning process by adjusting weight values through various algorithms (Amjad et al., 2022).

3.2. Classification Algorithms for Intrusion Detection System Datasets

Classification algorithms (KNN, SVM, and Random Forest) for intrusion detection experiments with the processed data sets are divided into two phases.

1. The training phase is pertinent to applying a classification algorithm to build and train a model using the training dataset, and
2. The classification model is evaluated in the testing phase using the testing data.

K-Nearest Neighbor Classifier algorithm pseudo-code follows sequential steps to classify (X, Y, x) //X: training data, Y: class labels of X, x: unknown sample.

For $i = 1$ to m do

 Compute distance $d(X_i, x)$

End for

 Compute set I containing indices for the k smallest distances $d(X_i, x)$

 Return the majority label for Y_i where $i \in I$

Support vector machine classifier

Support Vector Machines (SVMs) are a widely used classification algorithm in ML, particularly effective for binary classification. In the context of Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS), SVMs classify data into either an attack or non-attack class by identifying patterns within intrusion datasets. The core of SVM-based IDS classification involves mapping input data to its similarity based on the geometric characteristics of data structures within a feature space dimension. The process aims to pinpoint the most suitable class for a given input (Hani et al., 2023). Data is classified by defining a hyperplane decision boundary that maximizes the margin or space between itself and the nearest data points (known as support vectors) from each class. This approach effectively splits the database into two distinct classes, generating novel vectors with proper classification (Giampaolo et al., 2020). The objective is to find an optimal hyperplane that maximizes this margin between the support vectors of the two classes. For complex datasets, SVMs can transform the initial data space into a higher-dimensional feature space using a kernel function (Shin and Kim, 2020). This allows more effective linear separation in higher dimensions, thereby decreasing training errors. The resulting hyperplane is the decision boundary, as shown in Eq.2 and Figure 1.

$$h(x) = x^T \beta + \beta_0 = 0 \quad (2)$$

Subject to: x is the input vector of features. β : a vector of coefficients, and β_0 is a constant value. A vector point in space, the distance from a vector to the hyperplane boundary margin is:

$$(d) = \frac{|x^T \beta + \beta_0|}{\|\beta\|} \quad (3)$$

Figure 1: Support vector machine classifier

Random Forest

The Random Forest (RF) algorithm constructs a collection of decision trees from randomly chosen training data. It then

combines the votes from each decision tree randomly to determine the final class label. While suitable for detecting outliers in less sensitive data, Random Forest is particularly renowned for its exceptional accuracy and predictive power, making it an excellent classifier for handling large-scale datasets.

3.3. Proposed Hybrid Host-based Intrusion Detection Model

A Host-Based Intrusion Detection System (HIDS) analyzes data directly from a monitored host, including system calls, network events, and file system activity, to identify attack behaviors (Kopelo et al., 2013). Detecting network abnormalities within the host system is crucial for alerting system administrators to incoming threats. HIDS plays a vital role in identifying and classifying malicious code and unexpected behaviors, such as buffer overflows and unauthorized file system access. This often involves monitoring the file system, analyzing log files, scrutinizing network connections, and performing kernel-based intrusion detection.

Hybrid host-based intrusion detection models often combine anomaly-based (AHIDS) and signature-based (SHIDS) approaches (John et al., 2021). Anomaly-based HIDS works by visualizing deviations in system call activities from the host's normal data behavior (Amjad et al., 2022; Waqas et al., 2016). Any observation that falls outside these established normal circumstances is flagged as anomalous (Liu and Lang, 2019). In contrast, signature-based HIDS operates by comparing detected attack signatures against a database of known threats. When a match is found, the system triggers its defense mechanisms and issues an alert (Vasaki et al., 2022; Gideon and Jiankun, 2013). The training data used to build these models can originate from either the network (for network-based IDS) or the host (for host-based IDS). For network data, this might involve analyzing packet headers (Daniel, 2017) or modeling payloads (Guiling et al., 2011). At the host level, it typically traces modeling (Steven et al., 1998), where the HIDS model analyzes the sequence of system call task flow that the programs execute to achieve the correct results. The proposed model (Figure 2) architecture comprises two major components, as shown below.

Figure 2: Proposed Host-based Intrusion-Detection Model

The proposed anomaly-based instruction detection model, illustrated in Figure 2, outlines the research flow and incorporates machine learning algorithms as key components. This anomaly-based detection mechanism is particularly effective against novel (zero-day) attacks for which no matching signature exists in a reference database

(Zeeshan et al., 2020). The model begins with a pre-processing task to extract feature sets from raw ADFA-LD sequences of system calls data (Miao and Jiankun, 2014). This data is then represented using an N-gram mechanism, which generates feature sets based on the occurrence frequency and the number of times specific system calls appear within a sequence. After generating these N-gram feature sets, the most frequently occurring ones are selected for each 'n' value, with 'n' ranging from 1 to 5.

3.4. Open-Source Tools for Intrusion Detection Systems

Intrusion detection security tools help a network system operate optimally and safely from various illegal actions or malware (Francisco et al., 2021). OSSEC, SNORT, and Bro are commonly used intrusion detection tools for network-based and host-based IDS, typically utilizing a client/server architecture (Surya and Deepti, 2013; Pritika, 2012). The intrusion detection method processes within its kernel to monitor and receive information from agents (clients), Syslog, databases, and agentless devices. These systems can also manage and monitor distributed servers. In the OSSEC architecture (Figure 3), the server is the main framework, responsible for scanning, monitoring, detecting, and responding to threats found on hosts.

SNORT is a robust open-source network security tool that applies in intrusion detection, functioning effectively as both a HIDS and NIDS. It offers a real-time traffic analysis and packet logging across IP networks. Recognized as a powerful open-source network IDS (NIDS) (Marcin et al., 2021; Urooj et al., 2017). SNORT is adept at protocol analysis and content matching against predefined signatures. It is an indispensable tool for integrating machine learning into a rule-based approach to detect known attacks (Jose et al., 2018). SNORT achieves this through several key components: a packet sniffer, a preprocessor, a detection engine, and an alert/logging system that populates log files or databases with detection rules. The packet Sniffer initiates the process by capturing and matching packets, which are then passed to the preprocessor. This preprocessor checks the packets for specific plug-ins and behaviors before forwarding the data to the detection engine. In the detection engine, rules are applied to each packet to identify behaviors associated with known attacks. These rules are structured with rule headers that define required protocol fields and rule options to provide specific information matches and detect SNORT's response upon detection.

Figure 3: OSSEC architecture: the model depicts IDS performance procedures in ML and open-source methods.

4. Dataset Description and Preparation Procedures

Attack patterns are constantly changing, making it crucial to build a NIDS that can evolve in real-time to recognize both new network intrusion patterns and normal traffic data. One approach to detecting anomalous data that does not conform to normal circumstances involves developing a machine learning based model. The model creates a representation of multi-dimensional data, as highlighted by Ines et al. (2022). Machine learning attempts to learn data representations by stacking numerous nonlinear processing layers. Its core focus is on understanding data structure and capturing key statistical aspects to characterize data for classification and regression tasks. In this study, we utilize the ADF-LD dataset to evaluate the proposed model. The ADFA-LD data (Table 1) is publicly available for research and is divided into 833 for training and 4373 for validation. This trace dataset was gathered by executing various legitimate application activities, such as web browsing and document writing, during normal system operation when

no attacks were present.

Table 1: Structure of ADFA-LD data set

Data Type	Type of Traces	No. of Traces
Training dataset	Normal	833
Validation dataset	Normal	4373
Attack dataset	Add-user	91
	Hydra-FTP	162
	Hydra-SSH	176
	Java-Meterpreter	124
	Meterpreter	75
	Web-Shell	118

As detailed in Table 1, the ADFA datasets are processed with a thorough preprocessing procedure to achieve optimal accuracy with machine learning classifier algorithms. This process involves feature selection, where a Python script is used to define criteria and select representative feature vectors (N-grams). For attack data, a 70% training, 30% testing, and validation is implemented. According to Jain et al. (2021), the ADFA data is structured into designated training and validation folders, which are then used for the prediction model's training and testing mechanism.

4.1. Feature selection

Various mechanisms are employed for feature selection in anomaly detection, including analyzing the trace length (or short sequence mechanism) of each file, as noted by Waqas et al. (2016). Other methods involve identifying common patterns and counting occurrence frequencies, a technique highlighted by Gideon and Jiankun (2014). However, each of these approaches has its limitations. Relying solely on trace length can be insufficient for detecting anomalies, as pointed out by Miao et al. (2014). Similarly, using common patterns, consecutive system call IDs are often time-consuming. In contrast, frequency-based counting mechanisms, particularly those utilizing N-grams, stand out. N-grams are widely recognized as the most effective frequency-based method for generating feature sets and their occurrence frequencies from extensive sequences of system call data (Sagar and Kahate, 2013). This makes them a preferred choice for robust anomaly detection (Kayode et al., 2024).

4.2. N-Gram-based feature extraction

N-gram-based feature extraction is a technique that essentially breaks down a long sequence of system calls into shorter, arbitrary subsequences, or unigrams of N items. As Ramprakash et al. (2014) point out, these items can be incredibly versatile, representing anything from numbers and phonemes to syllables, letters, or even entire words, depending on the specific application. In this study, these items are numbers, specifically sequence system-call IDs (identifiers). Python script used to generate these N-gram features from the subsequences of the system call traces, exploring various lengths for N (N = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5). The weight value for N is determined empirically, meaning the selection process is based on the specific problem being solved and the characteristics of the intrusion data: a larger N value requires more space and processing time. The larger value of N requires more storage space and processing time. As the N increases, the number of unique attributes grows, but their occurrence frequency tends to decrease. Conversely, a smaller N value will result in a higher occurrence for the attributes.

Recent research in N-gram-based intrusion detection, as highlighted by Ehsan et al. (2017), indicates that the most commonly used and effective N values for N-gram-based feature extraction range from 1 to 5. To classify, an N-gram of size 1 (unigram) represents a sequence of a single number. A bi-gram corresponds to an N value of 2, signifying two-number sequences, while a tri-gram uses an N value of 3 for three-number sequences, and so forth. If they consider

'X' to be the number of systems call IDs in a given sequence 'k', then the number of N-grams for that sequence 'k' can be calculated using the following formula, Eq.1.

$$N - \text{grams}(sk) = X(N - 1) \tag{1}$$

If we have a sequence of system calls: "2, 3, 4, 3, 7, 3" and $N = 2$ (known as bigrams) (as eq.1), the number of N-grams in the given sequence is 5 ((2, 3) (3, 4) (4, 3) (3, 7) and (7, 3)), and for $N = 3$, the number of N-grams is 4: as (2, 3, 4) (3, 4, 3) (4, 3, 7) and (3, 7, 3), and so on.

Feature selection is the experimental identification of the subset of N-grams that are most informative. However, it is not likely that every N-gram is equally important for intrusion detection and classification. Non-informative features (N-grams) during training lead to a degradation of detection and classification accuracy, and the values of N range from 1 to 5 (1-gram, 2-gram, 3-gram, 4-gram, and 5-gram). The system call sequences are given in Figure 4 (it is the 3rd system call trace in the training file (UTD-0003) from the ADFA-LD data set). Therefore, the unique N-grams (1 gram, 2 grams, 3 grams, 4 grams, and 5 grams) with the corresponding occurrence frequency, and the number of N-gram tokens (using equation 1) are calculated in Figure 4.

1-gram	2-gram	3-gram	4-gram	5-gram
#Total No. of N-Gram Types: 24	#Total No. of N-Gram Types: 44	#Total No. of N-Gram Types: 52	#Total No. of N-Gram Types: 56	#Total No. of N-Gram Types: 59
#Total No. of N-Gram Tokens: 110	#Total No. of N-Gram Tokens: 109	#Total No. of N-Gram Tokens: 108	#Total No. of N-Gram Tokens: 107	#Total No. of N-Gram Tokens: 106
23 192	11 192 192	7 125 125 125	7 192 6 33 5	7 192 6 33 5 3
14 6	10 197 192	7 192 192 6	7 3 197 192 192	7 33 5 3 197 192
11 3	8 125 125	7 192 6 33	7 33 5 3 197	7 5 3 197 192 192
10 197	8 192 6	7 197 192 192	7 5 3 197 192	7 6 33 5 3 197
10 5	7 33 5	7 3 197 192	7 6 33 5 3	6 192 192 6 33 5
9 125	7 3 197	7 33 5 3	6 125 125 125 125	5 125 125 125 125 125
9 33	7 5 3	7 5 3 197	6 192 192 6 33	4 197 192 192 6 33
3 45	7 6 33 5	7 6 33 5	4 197 192 192 6	4 3 197 192 192 6
3 91	3 5 197	3 192 192 192	3 192 192 192 6	3 197 192 192 192 6
2 174	2 192 3	3 5 197 192	3 197 192 192 192	3 3 197 192 192 192
2 196	2 3 3	2 192 3 3	2 192 3 3 6	2 192 192 192 6 33
2 240	2 3 6	2 197 192 3	2 192 3 3 6	2 192 3 3 6 91
1 11	2 6 6	2 3 3 6	2 3 3 6 91	2 197 192 3 3 6
1 122	2 6 91	2 3 6 91	2 5 197 192 3	2 5 197 192 3 3
1 175	1 11 45	1 11 45 33	1 11 45 33 192	1 11 45 33 192 33
1 191	1 122 268	1 122 268 45	1 122 268 45 45	1 122 268 45 45 5
1 195	1 125 91	1 125 125 91	1 125 125 125 91	1 125 125 125 125 91
1 201	1 174 174	1 125 91 258	1 125 125 91 258	1 125 125 125 91 258
1 243	1 174 175	1 174 174 175	1 125 91 258 311	1 125 125 91 258 311
1 258	1 175 191	1 174 175 191	1 174 175 191 122	1 125 91 258 311 240
1 268	1 191 122	1 175 191 122	1 175 191 122 268	1 174 174 175 191 122
1 311	1 192 243	1 191 122 268	1 175 191 122 268	1 174 175 191 122 268
1 38	1 192 33	1 192 192 243	1 191 122 268 45	1 175 191 122 268 45
1 54	1 195 196	1 192 243 125	1 192 192 243 125	1 191 122 268 45 45
	1 196 196	1 192 33 5	1 192 192 6 192	1 192 192 192 6 192
	1 196 38	1 196 38	1 192 243 125 125	1 192 192 243 125 125
	1 201 54	1 192 6 192	1 192 33 5 197	1 192 192 6 192 192
	1 240 174	1 195 196 196	1 192 6 192 192	1 192 243 125 125 125
	1 240 240	1 196 196 38	1 195 196 196 38	1 192 33 5 197 192
	1 243 125	1 196 38 6	1 196 196 38 6	1 192 6 192 192 243
		1 197 192 6		

Figure 4: Calculated n-grams of the system call trace with the corresponding occurrence frequency for each value of n ($n = 1, 2, 3, 4,$ and 5).

5. Model performance evaluation metrics

To thoroughly evaluate machine learning-based Intrusion Detection System (IDS) models, we employ multiple performance evaluation metrics. A crucial tool in this process is the Confusion Matrix, which provides detailed information about both attack and non-attack classes within a given intrusion dataset, as noted by Muhammad and Kim (2021). The ID's data is manipulated to optimal execution information and visualized in a graph using the Y-axis (True Positive Rate (TPR)) and X-axis (False Positive Rate (FPR)) plot diagram. The classification algorithms that we use as a decision engine predict the probability of an instance within a given threshold range, which is smaller or larger than a specific threshold. It considers a part of a class as per the configuration.

The Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve is a powerful graphical tool that depicts the performance of a binary classification model by plotting the True Positive Rate (TPR) against the False Positive Rate (FPR) with all possible threshold values. ROC supports finding the optimal probability threshold where TPR-FPR is higher than FPR. The ROC curve is a visualization process that combines TPR and FPR. ROC curve-based evaluation follows the 45-degree diagonal line to represent all the required baseline classifiers. The ROC curve provides an overall performance measure of a model at all possible thresholds (John et al., 2021), and evaluation metrics are represented as follows.

- The True Positive Rate (TPR): It involves a machine learning classifier for ID's data classified as attack and non-attack classes, as eq. 4 & 5.

$$\text{True Positive Rate (TPR)} = TP / (TP + FN) \quad (4)$$

- The False Negative Rate (FNR): It processes the data, which is wrongly classified as attack instances.

$$\text{False Negative Rate (FNR)} = FP / (FP + TN) \quad (5)$$

Moreover, measuring performance in the confusion matrix supports that the diagonal elements correctly classify data, and the non-diagonal elements represent the wrongly classified datasets. It is visualized in Tables 3, 5, and 8, which show the attributes of the confusion matrix. The different evaluation metrics, including precision, Recall, F-measure, and ROC, are applied.

Precision: The ratio of correctly classified to all the samples classified as non-attack.

$$\text{Precision} = TP / (TP + FP) \quad (6)$$

Recall: it represents the proportion of actual positive samples that are correctly classified as positive by the model. This is found by dividing the number of true positives by the total number of true positives and false negatives.

$$\text{Recall} = TP / (TP + FN) \quad (7)$$

F-Measure: The ratio of the harmonic means of the Precision and Recall of the statistical technique to measure model accuracy.

$$F = 2 \left(\frac{\text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \right) \quad (8)$$

6. Experiment and Result Discussion

6.1. Classifier Model Development

Authors have successfully developed a host-based intrusion detection model specifically designed to identify outlier data points in various machine learning algorithms. To thoroughly assess the efficiency and robustness of this proposed model, its performance was rigorously evaluated using the well-known ADFA-LD dataset. The primary objective of the evaluation was to accurately classify instances as either an intrusion (attack) or normal activity (non-attack). The dataset's composition for training, testing, and validation was meticulously structured, as detailed in Table 2. Specifically, 60% of the Attack Data Master (ADM) was utilized from 100% of the Training Data Master (TDM) for the training phase. Concurrently, the remaining 40% of the Attack Data Master (ADM) was drawn from 100% of the Validation Data Master (VDM) to serve as the testing set. This strategic segmentation of data is essential, as size plays a significant role in determining the appropriate proportions for training, validation, and final testing, ensuring a comprehensive and unbiased evaluation of the model's capabilities.

Table 2: Training and testing data set arrangement

	TDM	VDM	ADM
Training Data	100%		60%
Testing Data		100%	40%

6.2. Model development using a binary class data set

In this study, Support Vector Machines, K-Nearest Neighbors, and Random Forests are used as classifiers. To understand how well each model performs using various metrics, including the detection rate (also known as recall or sensitivity) and the false-positive rate, among others.

6.2.1. Experiment using the SVM Algorithm

In this study, 1338 instances were used to train and test the proposed machine learning algorithms via Support Vector Machine (SVM) and perform a binary classification task to categorize data as either "attack" or "non-attack." The SVM model demonstrated strong performance, accurately classifying 1288 instances while misclassifying only 50. Delving into these misclassifications, as detailed in Table 3, revealed two types of errors: 24 non-attack instances were incorrectly identified as attacks (known as false positives), and 26 actual attack instances were mistakenly labeled as non-attacks (referred to as false negatives). It's important to note that out of 479 total attack instances within the given dataset, 809 instances were correctly classified as non-attack.

Table 3: SVM classifier on binary class ADFA-LD data set confusion matrix

a	b	Classified as
479	26	a = Attack
24	809	b = non-attack

Table 4 details the performance of SVM using standard performance measurement matrices. The result revealed that the True Positive Rate (TPR) for the non-attack class is 97.1%, while the False Positive Rate (FPR) is 5.1%. This indicates that 809 out of 833 non-attack traces were accurately identified, with the remaining 24 non-attack traces incorrectly classified as outliers.

Table 4: Performance of the SVM classifier on the binary class

TPR	FPR	Precision	Recall	F-Measure	ROC	Class
0.949	0.029	0.952	0.949	0.950	0.960	Attack
0.971	0.051	0.969	0.971	0.970	0.960	Non-attack
0.963	0.043	0.963	0.963	0.963	0.960	Weighted Avg.

The Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier demonstrated strong performance in the binary data classification task, achieving an impressive accuracy of 96.26%. This high level of accuracy was specifically obtained when utilizing 4-gram features for the classification process. Furthermore, the SVM classifier exhibited a remarkably low false-positive rate, averaging just 0.043%. This minimal rate of incorrectly identified positive instances was observed when the model leveraged all available n-gram features, as visually represented in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Performance of SVM classifier on binary class ADFA-LD data set using all n-gram features

6.2.2. Experiment using KNN Algorithm

The KNN-based machine learning algorithm is applied to summarize the binary class data set in Tables 5 and 6. In the confusion matrix, the 1294 traces from the 1338 data set are correctly classified under their respective classes. (810 non-attack TP and 484 attack TN traces data, in which 833 non-attack and 505 attack traces, respectively). And 23 non-attack and 21 attack traces are misclassified under their respective classes.

Table 5: Confusion matrix for KNN classifier on binary class

a	b	Classified as
484	21	a = Attack
23	810	b = non-attack

The model developed using the KNN classifier has achieved an accuracy (detection rate) of 96.71% with a 3.28% error rate. The remaining 44 of 1338 were misclassified under the contradictory classes. In Table 6, the overall classification performance is summarized. The number of False Positive rates for each of the results is less (an average of 0.036%).

Table 6: Detailed performance of the KNN classifier on the binary class

TPR	FPR	Precision	Recall	F-Measure	ROC	Class
0.958	0.028	0.955	0.958	0.957	0.997	Attack
0.972	0.042	0.975	0.972	0.974	0.997	Non-attack
0.967	0.036	0.967	0.967	0.967	0.997	Weighted Avg.

Figure 6 visualizes the performance of the KNN classifier as high with fewer n-gram features, which achieved 96% accuracy using 1-gram and 2-gram features. However, its accuracy with the remaining n-gram features, such as 3-gram, 4-gram, and 5-gram, is 93.2%, 85.72%, and 82.3%, respectively.

When dealing with high-dimensional data, the K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) algorithm faces significant challenges. Its computational efficiency drastically decreases, and the concept of "distance" between features becomes less meaningful, a phenomenon often referred to as the curse of dimensionality. The large-scale features are also more challenging for classification. On top of that, the way you pick K, which is the number of neighbors, really changes how the classification turns out. In the existing literature, a small value of K can make the model susceptible to noise, while a large value of K leads to increased computational expense. Through extensive experimentation, we determined that a value of K = 3 yielded the highest accuracy for our specific dataset. For example, when utilizing 1-gram features, we observed an accuracy of 96.41% with K = 3, compared to 94.84% with K = 5 and 93.87% with K = 7. The Euclidean distance metric was consistently used to calculate the proximity between data points.

Figure 6: KNN classifier performance on binary class data set for each of the n-gram features

6.2.3. Experiment using RF Algorithm

The Random Forest (RF) classifier demonstrated strong performance in binary classification tasks, effectively distinguishing between "non-attack" and "attack" datasets. Its results were comparable to those achieved by Support Vector Machines (SVM) and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN). Specifically, the Random Forest model reached an impressive 96.86% accuracy with a false-positive rate (FPR) of 3.9%. Delving into the specifics of the RF algorithm's output, it correctly classified 1296 traces while misclassifying only 42 traces. For the "non-attack" class, the FPR was 5%, meaning that out of 833 non-attack trace data points, 17 were incorrectly identified as attacks. More detailed insights into this tree-based class performance can be found in Tables 7 and 8.

Table 7: Detailed performance of the RF classifier on the binary class

TPR	FPR	Precision	Recall	F-Measure	ROC	Class
0.950	0.020	0.966	0.950	0.958	0.995	Attack
0.980	0.050	0.970	0.980	0.975	0.995	Normal
0.969	0.039	0.969	0.969	0.969	0.995	Weighted Avg.

Table 8: Confusion matrix for the RF classifier on the binary class

a	b	Classified as
480	25	a = Attack
17	816	b = Normal

As illustrated in Figure 7, the Random Forest classifier consistently demonstrated strong performance across different n-gram features when applied to the binary class ADFALD dataset. For most n-gram configurations, its performance remained remarkably stable, hovering around 96% accuracy. However, there was a noticeable dip in accuracy when using 3-gram features, resulting in a low performance of 92.53%.

Figure 7: Random forest classifier performance on a binary class data set

Generally, the performance of these three machine learning algorithms is high on each n-gram feature using a binary class data set. Figure 8 presents the performance results of the three classifiers for each of the n-gram features on the binary class data set.

Figure 8: Selected classification algorithms' performances on a binary class data set

We also conducted experiments by combining three (SVM, KNN, and RF) classifiers (voting ensemble classification) using "majority voting" rules. Tables 9 and 10 describe the performance of the voting ensemble classifier on the ADFA-LD binary class data set. And the voting, the classifier result has achieved higher performance than the individual classifiers for all n -gram features. As shown in Figure 9, the voting classifier outperforms 2-gram with an overall accuracy of 97.16%.

Table 9: Performance of voting ensemble classifier on the binary class data set

TPR	FPR	Precision	Recall	F-Measure	ROC	Class
0.962	0.023	0.962	0.962	0.962	0.993	Attack
0.977	0.038	0.977	0.977	0.977	0.993	Non-attack
0.972	0.032	0.972	0.972	0.972	0.993	Weighted Avg.

The confusion matrix, presented in Table 10 and visually represented in Figure 9, provides a clear picture of the classification results. Out of the total traces analyzed, 486 were accurately identified as attack traces, and 814 were correctly classified as normal traces. The matrix also revealed a small number of misclassifications: 19 normal traces were incorrectly flagged as attacks, and conversely, 19 attack traces were mistakenly categorized as normal. This performance yielded an impressively low false-positive rate of 0.032, a metric that significantly outperforms other comparable systems.

Table 10: Voting ensemble classifier on the binary class confusion matrix

a	b	Classified as
486	19	a = Attack
19	814	b = non-attack

Figure 9: Voting classifier Performance using the binary class ADFA-LD data set

6.3. Model performance evaluation using a multi-class dataset

The effectiveness of the proposed model was evaluated using the ADFA-LD dataset, a comprehensive benchmark specifically designed for multi-class network attack detection. The model was tested using three machine learning

algorithms: Support Vector Machine (SVM), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), and Random Forest (RF), with the ADFA-LD dataset for new trace instances classified as either benign or malicious. Subsequently, a more nuanced multi-classification strategy was implemented, enabling the model to provide a more detailed and actionable understanding of the detected threats.

The classification process was designed to identify six distinct attack types: Add user, Hydra FTP, Hydra SSH, Meterpreter, Java Meterpreter, and WebShell, using their corresponding trace files. However, this multi-classification task proved to be challenging due to the high degree of similarity between the trace files of different attack classes. This similarity made accurate classification difficult, resulting in a lower overall performance rate. A detailed analysis of the confusion matrix (Table 11) revealed that out of 505 total attack traces, only 289 were correctly classified, while the remaining 216 were incorrectly assigned.

As detailed in Tables 11 and 12, the Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier correctly identified 1093 out of 1338 trace files. The remaining 245 instances were misclassified across various categories. This lower performance in detecting attack classes, specifically reflected in a reduced True Positive Rate (TPR), is primarily attributed to the significant similarities in features among different trace files. Despite this challenge, the model demonstrated strong performance in identifying non-attack instances, achieving an impressive detection rate of 96.5%.

Table 11: SVM classifier performance result on a multi-class data set

TP Rate	FP Rate	Precision	Recall	F-Measure	ROC Area	Class
0.357	0.024	0.392	0.357	0.374	0.812	Add-user
0.704	0.039	0.628	0.704	0.664	0.847	Hydra-FTP
0.735	0.013	0.843	0.735	0.785	0.851	Hydra-SSH
0.512	0.041	0.457	0.512	0.483	0.848	Java-Meter
0.345	0.023	0.388	0.345	0.365	0.837	Meterpreter
0.513	0.017	0.645	0.513	0.571	0.888	Web-Shell
0.965	0.093	0.945	0.965	0.955	0.941	Non-attack
0.817	0.068	0.815	0.817	0.815	0.906	Weighted Avg.

In Table 11, the model achieved a maximum performance of 81.69% accuracy with an average false-positive rate of 6.8% when utilizing 4-gram features. This resulted in 804 instances (96.5%) being correctly classified under their respective classes. The remaining 19 (3.5%) were misclassified as attack traces, meaning (i.e., 3, 4, 4, 5, 9, and 4). Specifically, 3 non-attack traces are identified as Add-user, 4 as Hydra-FTP, 4 as Hydra-SSH, 5 as Java-Meterpreter, 9 as Meterpreter, and 4 as Web-shell attack traces. As discussed above, the lower the N value is, the lower the accuracy of the SVM algorithm performance and vice versa (Table 12). The higher the margin is, the lower the generalization error of the classifier.

Table 12: SVM classifier on a multi-class data set confusion matrix

a	b	c	d	e	f	g	Classified as
20	15	0	13	2	4	2	a = Add-user
9	81	7	2	0	4	12	b = Hydra-FTP
1	8	86	4	4	3	11	c = Hydra-SSH
10	10	2	43	10	5	4	d = Java-Meterpreter
2	4	2	16	19	2	10	e = Meterpreter
6	7	1	11	5	40	8	f = Web-Shell
3	4	4	5	9	4	804	g = Normal

Figure 10 summarizes the experimental results for the Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier across various n-

gram feature sets. The visualization distinctly illustrates a direct correlation between the classifier's performance and the scale of the features used. Specifically, the SVM model demonstrated higher accuracy and effectiveness when trained with larger-scale n-gram features, indicating that a richer and more detailed representation of the data significantly enhanced its ability to classify. Conversely, the model exhibited noticeably poorer performance when exposed to smaller n-gram features, suggesting that a limited feature set hindered its capacity to identify patterns and make accurate distinctions.

Figure 10: SVM detection performance on a multi-class ADFA-LD data set

When applied to the multi-class classification task on the ADFA-LD dataset, both the K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) and Random Forest (RF) algorithms, much like the Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier, exhibited comparatively poorer performance than what might be expected in a binary classification scenario. This decline in accuracy highlights the increased complexity of distinguishing among multiple attack categories, and subtle differences between classes can lead to misclassifications. As visually represented in Figure 11, the highest classification accuracy achieved by the KNN classifier reached 82.15%, while the Random Forest classifier slightly outperformed it with a peak accuracy of 84.75%. These figures underscore the challenges inherent in multi-class network intrusion detection, particularly when dealing with datasets that contain highly similar attack signatures.

The K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) and Random Forest (RF) classifiers demonstrated a high performance in accurately identifying instances of the non-attack class. As shown in Tables 13 and 14, the RF classifier was particularly effective, correctly categorizing 831 out of 833 non-attack traces. This remarkable result translates to a True Positive Rate of 99.8% for the non-attack class, indicating its strong ability to distinguish legitimate network activity. Only two instances were misclassified as attack classes: one trace was incorrectly identified as an Add-user attack, and the other as a Hydra-SSH attack.

Table 13: RF classifier result performance on ADFA-LD multi-class data set

TP Rate	FP Rate	Precision	Recall	F-Measure	ROC Area	Class
0.607	0.026	0.507	0.607	0.553	0.959	Add-user
0.730	0.020	0.778	0.730	0.753	0.940	Hydra-FTP
0.624	0.015	0.802	0.624	0.702	0.927	Hydra-SSH
0.583	0.026	0.598	0.583	0.590	0.924	Java-Meter
0.309	0.016	0.447	0.309	0.366	0.894	Meterpreter
0.590	0.015	0.708	0.590	0.643	0.924	Web-Shell
0.998	0.111	0.937	0.998	0.966	0.992	Non-attack
0.848	0.076	0.839	0.848	0.840	0.968	Weighted Avg.

Table 14: Confusion matrix for RF classifier

a	b	c	d	e	f	g	Classified as
34	6	1	6	4	4	1	a = Add-user

6	84	6	5	3	4	7	b = Hydra-FTP
1	12	73	3	4	4	20	c = Hydra-SSH
13	3	5	49	7	4	3	d = Java-Meterpreter
6	1	4	14	17	3	10	e = Meterpreter
6	2	1	5	3	46	15	f = Web-Shell
1	0	1	0	0	0	831	g = non-track

Figure 11 provides a visual summary of how the proposed three prominent machine learning algorithms—Support Vector Machine (SVM), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), and Random Forest (RF)—performed when applied to the ADFA-LD multi-class dataset. This illustration is crucial for understanding the comparative effectiveness of each algorithm in tackling the complex task of multi-class intrusion detection. It specifically highlights the varying degrees of success these models achieved in accurately classifying different types of cyber-attacks present in the dataset, allowing for a direct comparison of their strengths and weaknesses in this challenging real-world scenario.

Figure 11: SVM, KNN, and RF classifiers' performance on ADFA-LD multi-class data set

The True Positive Rate (TPR) for each attack and non-attack class is presented in Figure 12. The TPR for attack classes is low in each algorithm. For instance, in Figure 12a, the TPR of attack classes using 1-gram features is less than 22%.

All Meterpreter trace files are misclassified under other attack classes. The TPR for the non-attack class was above 96% in all n-gram features. The RF classifier result for non-attack traces gains high accuracy. As shown in Tables 15, 16, and 17 and Figures 12a, b & c, greater than 99% is achieved for each n-gram feature. Generally, attack trace files in the ADFA-LD data set have similar features, which makes it difficult to distinguish one attack file from the others.

Table 15: TPR for attack and normal classes on the ADFA-LD multi-class dataset using an SVM classifier

N-gram lists	Attack and Normal Classes						
	Add-user	Hydra-FTP	Hydra-SSH	Java-Meterpreter	Meterpreter	Web-Shell	Normal
1-G	1.80%	4.30%	18.80%	3.60%	0.00%	21.80%	99.20%
2-G	16.10%	69.60%	62.40%	45.20%	16.40%	52.60%	96.20%
3-G	32.10%	69.60%	74.40%	47.60%	21.80%	60.30%	96.00%
4-G	35.70%	70.40%	73.50%	51.20%	34.50%	51.20%	96.50%
5-G	32.10%	67.80%	70.90%	51.20%	27.30%	42.30%	97.50%

(a)

Table 16: TPR for attack and normal classes on the ADFA-LD multi-class dataset using the RF classifier

Attack and Normal Classes							
N-gram lists	Add-user	Hydra-FTP	Hydra-SSH	Java-Meterpreter	Meterpreter	Web-Shell	Normal
1-G	57.10%	73.00%	65.00%	51.20%	29.10%	67.90%	99.40%
2-G	60.70%	73.00%	62.40%	58.30%	30.90%	59.00%	99.80%
3-G	42.90%	67.00%	59.80%	52.40%	16.40%	66.70%	99.80%
4-G	44.60%	61.70%	59.00%	50.00%	18.20%	65.40%	99.90%
5-G	37.50%	52.20%	65.00%	46.40%	10.90%	42.30%	99.50%

(b)

Table 17: TPR for attack and normal classes on the ADFA-LD multi-class dataset using the KNN classifier

Attack and Normal Classes							
N-gram lists	Add-user	Hydra-FTP	Hydra-SSH	Java-Meterpreter	Meterpreter	Web-Shell	Normal
1-G	35.70%	68.70%	63.20%	52.40%	32.70%	66.70%	94.60%
2-G	29.20%	66.30%	68.90%	54.90%	38.80%	50.00%	96.20%
3-G	28.60%	73.00%	53.00%	41.70%	25.50%	42.30%	95.30%
4-G	28.60%	48.70%	53.00%	35.70%	20.00%	23.10%	97.20%
5-G	14.30%	37.40%	54.70%	21.40%	14.50%	15.40%	99.30%

Figure 12: The TPR attack classes in each algorithm

7. Conclusion

In this paper, the authors proposed a novel approach to enhance the intrusion detection process by integrating the strengths of both Host-based Intrusion Detection Systems (HIDS) and Network-based Intrusion Detection Systems (NIDS). The methodology leverages the ADFA-LD system traces data, which is meticulously categorized into non-attack and attack classes. To achieve this classification, various n-gram-based feature extraction techniques are employed, allowing for a detailed representation of the data for subsequent intrusion detection and analysis. Three prominent machine learning algorithms: Support Vector Machine (SVM), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), and Random Forest (RF) are utilized for detection and classification purposes. These algorithms were applied for anomaly-based detection, which identifies deviations from normal behavior, and signature-matching-based detection, which recognizes known attack patterns. The classification process specifically aims to categorize outcomes as either non-attack or various attack classes, relying on representative features derived from their similarity and occurrence frequency. The machine learning classifiers consistently achieved high performance in binary and multi-class classifications, as evidenced by standard metrics such as accuracy, false alarm rates, precision, and recall, as shown in the Tables. A key focus of this study was to minimize false positive alarms, a critical concern in intrusion detection due to their potential to generate unnecessary alerts and fatigue security analysts. For a practical demonstration, the authors configured the OSSEC tool on an Oracle virtual machine, successfully detecting intrusive activities occurring on the host. The OSSEC HIDS provides alert messages with 16 distinct severity levels (0 to 15), designed within a hybrid model that combines machine learning with OSSEC for superior detection capabilities. The advantage of this hybrid approach is that OSSEC (signature-based) can effectively detect known attacks, while the anomaly-based support enables the detection of new, zero-day attacks. It's important to note that as the value of 'n' in n-gram features increases (e.g., 4, 5, or more), the number of features grows substantially, which can lead to increased processing complexity and, paradoxically, less effective detection performance. Future work will delve deeper into exploring how similar features in trace files impact classification effectiveness. Further research, considering the classes of attacks and their granularity by incorporating more publicly available datasets.

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